

Characterization study of biodiesel from used frying oil

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Abstract : The utilization of liquid fuels such as biodiesel produced from used frying oil by transesterification process and it represents one of the most promising optional sources to replace the use of conventional fossil fuels. This study used two kinds of UFPO (palm oil), UFGO (groundnut oil) to characterization and optimization the biodiesel. The process variables are : methanol to oil molar ratio (3 : 1–12 : 1); catalysts (KOH, NaOH, CH₃OK and CH₃ONa); catalyst concentration (0.5, 1.0, 1.5 and 2.0 wt%); temperature (50, 55, 60 and 65 °C); time (30, 60, 90 and 120 min) and methanol used this experiment. In that, UFPO shows higher biodiesel yield than UFGO and the optimized biodiesel parameters were : KOH catalyst, 6 : 1 molar ratio, 1.0 wt% of catalyst concentration, 60 °C temperature, and 120 min reaction time. FTIR technique is used to identify the peaks formed in final biodiesel product in UFPO. These optimized biodiesel parameters are meets the quality specifications required by the European Standard for biodiesel, i.e. EN 14214 : 2010 and also Biodiesel were confirmed by FTIR technique.

Keywords : Biodiesel, used frying oil, transesterification, gas chromatography, palm oil.

Introduction

All over the world worry about the changes in environmental conditions due to the usability of non-renewable resources to transportation purposes. However, these sources are limited and will be exhausted quickly. So, alternative renewable fuels sources like biodiesel, bioethanol, and biofuels have potential to resolve the non-renewable one and it will improve sustainability of the environment. In this work, used frying oil can be used as a biodiesel sources and partially improve the global problems. In addition, the utilization of used frying oils diminishes the problems of contamination, because the re-using of these waste greases can reduce the burden of the government in disposing of the waste, maintaining public sewers, and treating the oil wastewater¹. The use of waste frying oil, instead of fresh oil, to produce biodiesel is an effective way to reduce the raw material cost because waste frying oil is estimated to be about half of the price of fresh oil². Hence, the use of waste cooking oils and non-edible oils should be given higher priority over the edible oils as biodiesel feedstock³. Generally, biodiesel is produced by means of transesterification reaction of oil

with an alcohol to form fatty acid methyl esters (FAME) and a byproduct of glycerol. Considerable research has been conducted to investigate the production of biodiesel from waste oil under acid⁴, alkaline^{5,6} and enzyme catalysis^{7,8}. Waste cooking oils exhibit properties different than those of refined and crude oils. The high temperatures of particular frying processes and the water from the foods accelerate the hydrolysis of triglycerides and increase the FFA content in the oil. Acid catalysis is more efficient when the amount of FFA in the oil exceeds 1%⁹. Though, acid-catalyzed transesterification is insensitive to FFA in the feedstock; it requires longer reaction time and higher temperature. Many researchers recommend using acid-catalysis as pretreatment step followed by alkaline catalyzed step⁴. Wang *et al.* (2007) were adopted this kind of two-step catalyzed process to prepare biodiesel from used frying oil¹⁰. Nevertheless, some researchers¹¹⁻¹³ have pointed out that the alkali-catalyzed transesterification could be completed as long as the FFA content in the oil is not greater than 1% and all materials should be substantially anhydrous.

In this paper, used frying oil is source neither used nor wasted and is one of the most economical choices to produce biodiesel. Since one of the major concerns on biodiesel production is the price of feedstock, utilization of used frying oil significantly enhances the economic viability of biodiesel production.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

The material sources were : used frying oils are collected from local restaurants with high FFA content. Methyl alcohol of 99.9% purity was purchased from SD Fine Chemicals, Mumbai. The catalysts like KOH pellets of 98.2% purity, NaOH pellets of 97% purity, CH₃OK powder of 98% purity, CH₃ONa powder of 98% purity were purchased from Nice Chemicals, Kerala. FTIR technique values were obtained from Sophisticated Equipments Laboratories, Department of Chemistry, Anna University, Chennai.

Experimental procedure :

Used frying oil is collected from local restaurants and heated to 110 °C and removes the water molecules then filter by 10 µm cloth to separate all food waste and suspended materials. Generally, biodiesel production is strongly influenced by FFA content of the used frying oil and the amount of catalyst had impact of conversion of esters during the transesterification process. So, a two-stage process is followed to convert the biodiesel from used frying oil. First stage, an acid-catalyst (sulfuric acid) was used to esterify (pretreatment) the used frying oil. The mixture was vigorously stirred for 1.5 h at 50 °C. After reaction, the mixture was filtered and the unreacted methanol was separated from the liquid phase via distillation. The pretreated oil is washed three times with sodium chloride solution and then dried using anhydrous sodium sulfate. After the pretreatment, the FFA value of the pretreated oil was lesser than that of freshly used cooking oil.

This esterification reaction was described as below :

The second stage, a homogeneous catalyst (NaOH, KOH, CH₃ONa and CH₃OK) is used to transesterify the pre-

treated oil :

The reaction procedure was as follows : first, the catalyst was dispersed in methanol using stirring system was connected to it. Then, the pretreated oil was added into the strirring mixture and heated to 50 °C for three hours. After thorough mixing and kept it overnight; two layers were formed. In that, the upper layer consists of biodiesel whereas the lower layer consists of glycerin and this layer consist of excess methanol, unreacted catalyst and soap. This unreacted methanol was distilled off under a vacuum condition while biodiesel layer was separated with the help of separating system and finally remaining glycerin layer is separated and then distilled to get 98% purified glycerin. The separated biodiesel is purified with hot water until the pH gets neutral¹⁴.

Results and discussion

Effect of catalyst :

Free fatty acids (FFAs) content after acid esterification should be minimal or otherwise less than 2% FFAs. These FFAs react with the alkaline catalyst to produce soaps instead of esters. It depicts the effect of FFAs on the yield of methyl ester during alkali catalyzed transesterification. There is a significant drop in the ester conversion when the free fatty acids are beyond 2%¹⁵. The acid value of UFPO is 4.61% and UFGO is 4.95%. Fig. 1 (un esterified oil) represents the experiments carried out with 6 : 1 molar ratio of alcohol to oil used with 1 wt% of base catalysts, 60 min reaction time at 60 °C and it represents UFPO gave higher biodiesel yield than UFGO and because of its nature of FFA content. After pretreatment process, the acid value of UFPO is 1.57% and UFGO is 1.95%. Now, this pretreated oil used with given base catalysts at 60 °C of 6 : 1 molar ratio of alcohol to oil, 1 wt% of base catalysts and 60 min reaction time. Fig. 2 describes KOH shows better biodiesel

Fig. 1. Biodiesel yield with UFO (UE).

Fig. 2. Biodiesel yield with UFO (E).

yield behavior than other base catalysts used here for both UFPO and UFGO and also indicates hydroxides gave higher yield than corresponding to methoxides. Naturally, KOH is frequently soluble in solvent and easily promote the reaction. Generally, catalyst concentration can affect the rate of biodiesel reaction and beyond the limitation of catalyst additions it represented in Fig. 3. So, KOH catalyst used with 0.5, 1.0, 1.5, 2.0 wt% concentration for

Fig. 3. Biodiesel yield with KOH concentration.

both UFPO and UFGO in that, 0.5 wt% of KOH shows only 38% and 43% biodiesel yield for UFPO and UFGO. For, 2.0 wt% catalyst shows biodiesel yield to 50% and 63% decreases due to its higher concentration of catalyst addition gives negative effect of biodiesel production. Whereas describes 1.0 wt% of catalyst shows higher biodiesel yield than other concentrations. In general, as the catalyst concentration increased, the conversion of triglycerides also increased. In basic catalyst, a slight decrease in ester content was observed in the experiments with 1.5 wt% of catalyst with regard to the experiments with 1 wt%. This is because the addition of excess alkaline catalysts caused more triglycerides participation in the saponification reaction, resulting in increased production of soap and mentioned reduction of the esters yield¹⁶. So, any increase in concentration of catalyst beyond the neutralization limit results in decrease in biodiesel conversion. These results are very similar to those found in the literature in transesterification processes of used frying oil with methanol and other alcohols that also concluded that potassium hydroxide was the best catalyst^{17,18}.

Effect of temperature :

The primary advantage of higher temperatures influences to shorter reaction time. However, higher reaction temperatures causes methanol to vaporize resulting in decreased yield. In this process, the temperature ranges used 50, 55, 60 and 65 °C and in order to optimize biodiesel yield with using the constant parameters are : alcohols to oil molar ratio of 6 : 1 with KOH concentration of 1 wt% for UFPO and UFGO at 60 min reaction time. Fig. 4 describes biodiesel yield with respect to temperature ranges of 50, 55, 60 and 65 °C for both UFPO

Fig. 4. Biodiesel yield with temperature.

and UFGO. 50 °C shows, biodiesel yield were 73% for UFPO and 60% for UFGO again increases the temperature to 55 °C and biodiesel yield also increases. Further the temperature increases to 60 °C, the biodiesel yield were 94% for UFPO and 85% for UFGO. At 65 °C, biodiesel yield were 85% for UFPO and 73% for UFGO. When the temperature decreases, the rate of reaction also decreases. Therefore, the equilibrium concentration was strongly conditioned by the temperature and favored for the same; that is, the equilibrium concentration increased as the temperature increased. Therefore the optimum temperature is 60 °C for UFPO and UFGO biodiesel process. Encinar *et al.* (2007) explained three temperatures like 35, 60, 78 °C for used frying oil in 12 : 1 molar ratio of methanol-oil condition with 1 wt%. But in that 60, 78 °C temperatures show almost same curve, whereas in the present case three temperatures show different curve with 6 : 1 ratio and 1 wt% of KOH used¹.

Effect of reaction time :

According to many researchers, the biodiesel yields are directly proportional to the reaction times used. This experiment was conducted from the reaction time of 30, 60, 90 and 120 min with the constant parameters : 60 °C of reaction temperature for 1 wt% of KOH catalyst used in 6 : 1 molar ratio of UFPO and UFGO. Fig. 5 show that effect longer mixing gives higher yield than using shorter time. So, 90 min of reaction time gave a good

Fig. 5. Biodiesel yield with reaction time.

result than other reaction times used here. In other words, the biodiesel yields increases with increasing the reaction time. However, based on the results, it shows that the biodiesel yields were lower when reaction time of 120 min was used. This undesirable result may be due to the

higher soap formation when longer reaction time was used. Thus, the rate of soap formation was also increased.

Effect of molar ratio :

Generally, the stoichiometry of the reaction requires 3 moles of methanol per mole of triglycerides to yield 3 moles of biodiesel and 1 mole of glycerol. Methanol is a commonly used alcohol for transesterification because of its low price and highly reactive nature¹⁹. In this experiment, UFPO and UFGO were used with varying molar ratios of methanol and oil (3 : 1, 6 : 1, 9 : 1 and 9 : 1) and 1.0 wt% KOH at 60 °C with 60 min reaction time as represented in Fig. 6. As mentioned, the transesterification activity also depends on the molar concentrations of methanol to oil and also associated with the type of catalyst

Fig. 6. Biodiesel yield with molar ratio.

used. If the molar ratio increased from 3 : 1 to 6 : 1 and then biodiesel yield content also increased for UFPO as well as UFGO. Now, molar ratio increases from 6 : 1 to 9 : 1, methyl esters content decreased biodiesel yield and excess of molar ratio increases much then biodiesel yield also increases. Excess of methanol is required to shift the equilibrium favorably during transesterification for better yields of biodiesel. Therefore, 6 : 1 molar ratio gives a better result than other molar ratios and also repeated same procedure done for UFPO and UFGO. The higher alcohol molar ratio interferes with the separation of glycerol because there is an increase of solubility. In addition, an excess of alcohol was able increase the conversion of di-mono glycerides, but there is possibility of recombination of esters and glycerol to form mono glycerides because their concentration and also increasing during the course of the reaction, in other words the reactions

conducted with low molar ratios. Many researchers have reported an alcohol to oil molar ratio of 6 : 1 to be the optimal ratio, while²⁰ reported that the maximum biodiesel production was obtained at a molar ratio of 7 : 1 in transesterification of used frying oil.

Fuel specification :

The biodiesel obtained by KOH catalyst transesterification of used frying oil for 1.0 wt% KOH at 60 °C, 6 : 1 molar ratio with 90 min was analyzed by specific methods to determine physico-chemical characteristics that indicate its quality compared to quality specifications required by the European Standard for biodiesel (equivalent to ASTM specifications), i.e. EN 14214 : 2010 and biodiesel fuel specifications were tabulated in Table 1. The following physico-chemical characteristics were determined : ester content, density at 15 °C, visco-

Table 1. Biodiesel fuel specifications

Biodiesel parameters	KOH	Standard EN14214	
		Min	Max
Methyl ester (w/w %)	96.30	96.5	-
Density at 15 °C (kg/m ³)	893	860	900
Viscosity at 40 °C (cSt)	4.87	3.50	5.00
Flash point (°C)	154	120	-
Sulphur content (mg/kg)	0.05	-	10
Water content (mg/kg)	150	-	500
Acid value (mg KOH/g)	0.42	0.5	-
Iodine value (g I ₂ /100 g)	114	120	-
Monoglyceride content, % (m/m)	0.12	-	0.80
Diglyceride content, % (m/m)	0.07	-	0.20
Triglyceride content, % (m/m)	0.04	-	0.20
Free glycerol, % (m/m)	0.00	-	0.02
Total glycerol, % (m/m)	0.21	-	0.25
Calorific power, (MJ/kg)	36.43	-	-

sity at 40 °C, flash point, sulphur content, water content, acid value, iodine value, methanol content, mono-di-triglycerides content, free and total glycerol content, and calorific power. These fuel parameters are that directly influence as on engine parameters.

FTIR spectra confirmation :

In this study, FTIR technique is used to identify the frequency peaks are formed with respect to the % transmittance. A detailed FTIR frequency description was given for UFPO with biodiesel peaks result of KOH catalysts.

Fig. 7 shows the FTIR spectrum of UFPO. The spectrum was characterized with asymmetric and symmetric strong stretching vibrations of carboxyl group at 2675.6 cm⁻¹,

Fig. 7. FTIR spectrums for UFPO.

along with the O-H stretching of the hydroxyl bonded with alcohol at 3461.3 cm⁻¹ and aldehyde, ketones (C=O) group along with carboxylic group at 1747.2 cm⁻¹. C-O group combined with carboxylic group at 1238.9, 1165.4 cm⁻¹. So, this peaks confirmed the oil functional groups. Fig. 8 shows the FTIR spectrum of biodiesel for KOH catalyst for UFPO. The spectrum was characterized with asymmetric and symmetric strong stretching vibrations of carboxyl group at 3000–2500 cm⁻¹, along with the

Fig. 8. FTIR spectrums of biodiesel for UFPO.

O-H stretching of the hydroxyl bonded with alcohol at 3600–3200 cm^{-1} (broad) with alcohols, phenols groups. Aldehyde, ketones (C=O) group along with carboxylic group, ester group strongly stretched found at 1744.0 cm^{-1} (1470–1670 cm^{-1}). C–O group combined with carboxylic group, ester group strongly stretched at 1169.9 cm^{-1} (1260–1000 cm^{-1}). So, above frequency peaks are confirmed the biodiesel (methyl ester) formation KOH catalyst.

Conclusions

Used frying oil is an effect source for transesterification of biodiesel. The optimized biodiesel parameters : The methanol/oil molar ratio 6 : 1; catalyst concentration of 1.0 wt%; temperature ranges of 60 °C and KOH gave the highest biodiesel yield. The FTIR technique identified, UFPO is obtained the carboxyl group at 2675.6 cm^{-1} , along with the O–H stretching of the hydroxyl bonded with alcohol at 3461.3 cm^{-1} and carboxylic group at 1747.2 cm^{-1} . C–O group combined with carboxylic group at 1238.9, 1165.4 cm^{-1} . FTIR spectrum of biodiesel for KOH catalyst show asymmetric and symmetric strong stretching vibrations of carboxyl group at 3000–2500 cm^{-1} , along with the O–H stretching of the hydroxyl bonded with alcohol at 3600–3200 cm^{-1} (broad) with alcohols. Ester group strongly stretched found at 1744.0 cm^{-1} . C–O group combined with carboxylic group, ester group strongly stretched at 1169.9 cm^{-1} .

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Abbreviation

UFO - Used Frying Oil, UFPO - Used Frying Palm Oil, UFGO - Used Frying Groundnut Oil, FTIR - Fourier Transmission Infra Red Response.

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